

Engaging Faculty and Reducing Costs by Leveraging Collections: A Pilot Project to Reduce Course Pack Use

Nelly Cancilla

Communications and Liaison Librarian, University of Toronto Libraries

Bobby Glushko

Associate University Librarian, Research and Scholarly Communication, Western University

Stephanie Orfano

Acting Head, Copyright and Scholarly Communications, University of Toronto Libraries

Graeme Slaght

Copyright Outreach Librarian, University of Toronto Libraries

INTRODUCTION Academic libraries have the privilege of serving many roles in the lives of their institutions. One role that is largely untapped is their ability to actively leverage their collections to support faculty teaching and to reduce student out-of-pocket costs by eliminating systemic double payment for course materials. **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM/SERVICE** This paper details a project by the Scholarly Communications and Copyright Office (SCCO) at the University of Toronto that aimed to reduce this systemic double payment by leveraging collections and electronic reserves to provide a new service, the Zero-to-Low Cost Courses. Building on existing relationships with faculty, SCCO staff reached out to potential candidates, identified library licensed materials in their printed course packs, and created digital course packs which students could use at no cost. **NEXT STEPS** This article shares the results of the project and explores next steps in using existing library resources to actively reduce student course costs.

Received: 04/07/2016 Accepted: 08/02/2016

Correspondence: Graeme Slaght, University of Toronto Libraries, 130 St. George Street, Toronto, Ontario, graeme.slaght@utoronto.ca

© 2016 Slaght et al. This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

INTRODUCTION

Over the course of the 2014-2015 academic year, the Scholarly Communications and Copyright Office (SCCO) at the University of Toronto devised and conducted the Zero-to-Low Cost Course (ZTLCC) pilot project. The project's aims were twofold: first, to explicitly reduce the cost of course materials for students, and second, to do this in a way which would address the systemic unnecessary double payment by students for course materials already available to them through the collections and services of the University of Toronto Libraries. Through the project's targeted outreach to faculty members who were using course packs to distribute their assigned course readings, twelve courses with a combined enrollment of 877 students participated. As a result, these students saved a total of \$107,177.51 CAD (an average of \$122.20 each). With the support of the collections and copyright expertise of the SCCO, instructors of these participating courses assigned, to the greatest extent possible, open access content, public domain content, content that may be used freely as fair dealing under the Copyright Act, and content for which the library already held a license, all of which was made available electronically through the library's e-reserve service.

The project succeeded in leveraging existing library collections and services through active outreach that focused explicitly on reducing student cost through the efficient use of the existing collection. This is distinct from other efforts which focused on financial incentives directed at individual faculty participation (Bell, 2015). This success demonstrates the often hidden value of library collections within the political economy of scholarly communications, and points to ways to enhance the impact of existing library services.

Background

The cost of post-secondary education in the United States and Canada has increased substantially over the past few decades (Farrington, 2015; Habib, 2013). As state and provincial funding support for the operations of public academic institutions has decreased, students and their families have borne a large and increasing share of the balance of the funding that supports universities and colleges (Macdonald & Shaker, 2014). One substantial cost lurking within the price of education is the additional amount students must spend on textbooks, course packs, and on other supplemental materials, with one 2012 study finding that undergraduate students in Canada spend an average of \$385 per semester on course materials (Usher, 2015). In this vein, the Financial Consumer Agency of Canada recommends that undergraduate students set aside \$800 to \$1,000 per year for books and other materials (FCAC, 2014). These figures are large and have increased substantially over time: the US Government Accountability Office found that textbook prices have increased by 82 percent over the past decade, at an average rate of 6 percent per

year, well over the rate of inflation (U.S. GAO, 2013). These numbers suggest that even with the efficiencies gained through the digitization of course materials and the wide availability of used textbooks and textbook renting, the price tag for course materials remains steep, is growing, and has a real impact on the quality of undergraduate education. Given that most students fund their tuition and course materials costs at least partly through taking on a student loan, this impact is compounded over time.

This past year at the University of Toronto, some anecdotal instances of increased student cost in one particular segment of the course materials market, that of course packs, received attention in the student press. According to this coverage, course packs had become more expensive as a direct result of the decision by the University of Toronto to not renew its collective license agreement with the Canadian copyright collective licensing agency, Access Copyright.¹ A student told the University of Toronto student newspaper *The Varsity*, “my... professor told the class we would have to buy [the] course pack for nearly double the price it cost last year due to the termination of the Access Copyright license” (Robin 2014). Similar anecdotal stories have appeared at other institutions, as a growing number of universities and colleges in Canada have decided that the collective license agreement with Access Copyright was not worth the price at which it was being offered in negotiations, given the possibility of managing copyright costs internally. (More recently, students at Ryerson University expressed similar shock and disappointment with rising course pack costs in the aftermath of the expiration of Ryerson’s agreement with Access Copyright) (Chandler, 2016). As these student press articles show, there are undoubtedly some instances in which costs to students did rise significantly. However, depending on whether the instructor or producer of a given course pack was aware of the extent of their rights under Canadian copyright law and the contents of their library’s collections, these increased costs may have been unnecessary.

Project Design and Context

It was in response to the concerns of students and the above cited economic realities, and building on similar pre-existing services at the University of Toronto, that the Scholarly Communications and Copyright Office devised and ran the Zero-to-Low Cost Course (ZTLCC) pilot project, which aimed to engage faculty, specifically those who use course packs, in the creation of zero-to-low cost courses for their students. We were convinced that

¹ Up until 2013, each University of Toronto student paid \$26 per year to Access Copyright. While accounts of the many failed negotiations with Canadian universities and colleges differ, in 2014 Access Copyright unveiled the “Access Premium” license prices at \$15 per student. Although less than their previous offering, this license was not greeted with particular enthusiasm (Geist, 2014).

in examining the contents of course packs more closely, we would find evidence of systemic double payment for resources already held in the library's print and electronic collections, and that, by substituting a course pack with digitally-provided materials, we could produce significant efficiencies and savings for students. The pilot's concentration on course packs is also partly a result of the way that Canadian copyright law has evolved over the last fifteen years, especially since the 2012 reform of the Copyright Act and the jurisprudential clarifications of Canadian copyright law known as the "Copyright Pentalogy." These recent developments, especially the reaffirmation by the Supreme Court of Canada of fair dealing as a user's right that should be given a large and liberal interpretation and the subsequent legislative inclusion of "education" as a listed purpose under this statutory exception, have led to a reassessment of the way course materials and their copying are managed, paid for, and accessed by post-secondary students and their institutions. At the University of Toronto this ongoing assessment led to a significant investment in the internal management of copyright compliance through the creation and staffing of the Scholarly Communications & Copyright Office, a new unit within the library, as well as the concurrent development of an institutional policy, the University of Toronto's Fair Dealing Guidelines. The Canadian Supreme Court, in its landmark 2004 CCH decision, stated that a determination of whether or not an instance of educational copying is infringement or fair dealing can be made based either on the evaluation of the individual instance of copying or on an evaluation of the soundness of the institutional policies and practices of a given organization where such copying takes place. As long as such an institutional fair dealing policy is "research-based and fair," (*CCH Canadian Ltd v Law Society of Upper Canada*, 2004, at para 63 [CCH]) then copying performed in accordance with the policy can be said to be fair as well. As a result, Canadian academic institutions have adopted fair dealing guidelines, especially after the inclusion of "education" as a listed purpose under the exception (the number of institutions who began this reassessment before the creation of this purpose is a small but significant one; see below).

The Scholarly Communications & Copyright Office was designed to provide services on a year-round schedule, however, given the necessarily seasonal nature of academic work, there is an ebb and flow to the extent of the demand for the office's resources. As a result, the ZTLCC project was designed with these peaks and valleys of demand for service in mind. Outreach and assessment work was scheduled to bookend the project in non-peak periods, whereas the bulk of the work, the processing and provision of materials, was blended into the office's overall electronic reserve service. The ZTLCC was a natural next step from the work of clearing instructor syllabi for copyright compliance and of processing scans and links to electronic resources; little additional work was needed, because for the purposes of these tasks, a ZTLCC course was no different from any other course that was processed. In fact, non-ZTLCC copyright clearance work likely resulted in other savings in courses, but these

savings were and continue to be more difficult to measure without an immediate contextual link to the previous use of a course pack. Therefore, the effort allocation for the project was proportional to copyright clearance work at pre-peak and post-peak times. Overall, approximately 60 staff hours over a 14 week period were allocated, with the processing and copyright clearance of assigned course material taking up the bulk of this time. This moderate effort allocation was made more efficient by several factors: the quality and extent of the UTL collection; the level of staff expertise; and the clarity and usability of the Fair Dealing Guidelines, which played a significant part in making copyright compliance issues more manageable. As outlined in the workflow chart below, there were four major steps involved in the start to finish processing of ZTLCC courses: compliance, processing, content transfer, and data entry. Designated staff were assigned duties based on the already existing workflow for course reserves processing, except for data entry and assessment, which were the only additional tasks added to the work of the office by the ZTLCC project.

Figure 1. Typical Syllabus Service and ZTLCC workflow.

The University of Toronto’s Fair Dealing Guidelines (2012) contain both a standard and a rule. For one of the six fair dealing factors, that of the “amount of the dealing,” the guidelines recommend a rule-based approach to determining fairness by the length of copied excerpts. (The suggested maximum is 10 percent of a book or one chapter, whichever is greater.) Even while containing this rule, the policy recognizes that copying can be fair even if it exceeds the rule’s quantitative thresholds due to an analysis of the other fair dealing factors (or unfair even if fits within them). However,

for the purposes of the pilot project, reliance on the rule-based thresholds allowed us to efficiently determine whether or not a course pack reading could be distributed to students electronically without permission, or whether a transactional license might be necessary. A rule-based approach to fairness provided sounder footing for the increased formalization, centralization, and scale of e-reserves services within the University of Toronto Libraries, of which this project is an example. While recent legal developments in the United States might pose problems for the responsible application of a bright line fair use analysis (see below), Canadian courts and administrative bodies have been largely supportive of such quantitative tools (*CCH Canadian Ltd v Law Society of Upper Canada*, 2004, and more recently, *Access Copyright v. CMEC*, Copyright Board Canada, 2016). Furthermore, while much of the negative discussion on fair dealing in Canada has focused on publisher losses, 55% of the materials included in the course packs were already licensed by the library and were fully available in electronic form. *That is, publishing revenues for these resources were inflated by pervasive, sector-wide, systemic double payment.* This systemic double payment for content is deeply problematic and bears further scholarship and inquiry.

The pilot project is not without conceptual precedent; the University of California at Los Angeles (UCLA) Library, under the direction of Dr. Sharon Farb, Associate University Librarian for Collection Management and Scholarly Communication, has developed a project in this area to great success (UCLA, 2016). However, there are substantial differences in approach that distinguish the UCLA project, and others like it, from the ZTLCC project. The UCLA Affordable Course Materials Initiative targeted faculty who taught with assigned textbooks and incentivized faculty adoption of other forms of course materials by offering a direct cash reward, and, later, collection development funding for participating faculty members' research areas. By contrast, the ZTLCC pilot recruited the participation of faculty who used print course packs specifically and did not offer any form of individual financial incentive. Instead, the project relied on a direct outreach strategy to faculty that emphasized specialized assistance in developing a cost-free course reading list as well as the strength of the library collection, such that, *in nearly all cases, the actual materials included in the reading lists changed very little, if at all.* The conversation around how to engage faculty in the discussion about course materials costs and, more broadly, the costs of scholarly literature in general, often addresses the problem of the misalignment of faculty incentives with low-cost or cost-free publishing models (Warlick & Vaughan, 2007; Nariani & Fernandez, 2012; Migheli & Ramello, 2013). One theory that is fairly representative of explanations of this misalignment is that of R. Preston McCafee, who analogizes faculty behavior with the economic concept of "moral hazard" (Cohen, 2008). Because instructors and faculty assign and use materials without being personally (financially) implicated by the costs of their choices, a market

inefficiency is created, and as McCafee's argument goes, course material costs grow out of proportion to their real value due to a lack of a functional market to regulate their price. Free to consider their course materials (or publishing) decisions without regard to cost, other factors (such as convenience, inertia, or perceived quality) determine what materials students are assigned by instructors.

In this context, we believe that the uniqueness of the ZTLCC pilot project is twofold:

1. It successfully engaged faculty in a project about scholarly communication costs without reliance on a direct incentive, financial or otherwise.
2. It addressed existing inefficiencies in the scholarly communication system through the leveraging of existing library services and collections, rather than through the creation of wholly new, open access materials.

We believe that this pilot project has persuasively demonstrated that, combined with an aggressive outreach strategy and the judicious application of the flexibilities that copyright law provides (e.g., fair dealing), library collections can have a substantial impact on controlling and reducing student costs, in this case, costs related to the purchase of course packs; furthermore, this outreach can also begin to address the systemic double payment for scholarly resources that is endemic within the scholarly publishing ecosystem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Universities and colleges have met the related challenges of course materials cost and technological change in various ways. The explicit reduction of student costs through the digital distribution of materials has met a number of roadblocks. Among these impediments have been uncertainty about copyright restrictions and the ongoing assessment of the pedagogical value of digital learning materials. McGeveran and Fisher (2006) found that educational institutions were limited in the ways they could use technology to deliver instruction and low-cost instructional materials to their students. In particular, they pointed to copyright law's shaping of "business and institutional structures" (p. 7) within universities and colleges, such that the efficient sharing of electronic scholarly materials with students was inhibited by organizational inertia and countervailing interests within institutions (such as the business models of university bookstores, for example). Bridges (2007), in describing a threat of litigation made to Cornell University, wrote that "E-reserves practices ... vary widely and are influenced by institutional organizational structures, the information and technology infrastructure, manpower, demand, and the copyright law" (p. 317). Goodson and Frederiksen (2011) provide an overview of the multiple models of e-reserve delivery across a survey of ARL institutions, placing services on a spectrum between full service

and self-service, with many hybrids in between. Goodson and Frederiksen also point out that by 2011 many US institutions were reducing or disbanding their services in this area, allowing the work of administering electronic course materials to be decentralized to individual academic units or instructors through campus-wide LMS systems. In the U.S., this decentralizing trend has been encouraged by the most recent ruling in the Georgia State e-reserve case. In Canada, the University of Guelph and the University of Windsor began offering expanded e-reserve services to faculty, including copyright and licensing advice, well before other comparable Canadian institutions. Emily Hudson's (2014) ongoing research into the question of organizational inertia in Canada in terms of institutional response to the clear liberalization of copyright protections should underline how and why this slow response to change occurred. While some Canadian institutions read the CCH decision's endorsement of the use of "bright line" fair dealing policies and acted accordingly, most waited until after the re-affirmation of the CCH decision in 2012 (*Alberta (Education) v. Access Copyright*, 2012) to adopt or develop their own fair dealing standards. This adoption by Canadian institutions of guidelines that contain "bright line" rules for the determination of fair dealing now seems to be a clear distinguishing feature of Canada's copyright regime as compared to the retrenchment of such quantitative measures in the U.S.

Katz (2015) has contextualized the response by Canadian educational institutions to the reaffirmation of fair dealing as a user's right (and of the validity of institutional policies as arbiters of the application of this right) with an analogy to the stages of human development. According to Katz, "copyright adulthood" entails the design of policies that first and foremost empower researchers and students at institutions of higher learning to do what is "reasonably necessary" for their purposes under their rights granted to them by copyright law. Katz posits this mature stage as an evolution from earlier stages which instead instituted policies that simply mitigated institutional litigation risk by proscribing, setting limits on or policing behaviour. However, as Cunningham (2010) pointed out, developing a sophisticated or "adult" e-reserve service requires not only the crafting of sound policies but a substantial investment, or series of investments, particularly in "operational costs" (p. 225): in staff trained in copyright and license negotiation, in staff time for processing and arranging access to material, and in training and development related to integrating new software applications into existing library and institutional systems and workflows.

Evans and Willinsky (2013) identify course packs as a scholarly communications technology in need of attention and possible elimination and identify the course pack as "the site of major intellectual property battles" (p. 341) on campuses. They describe course packs as "among the least memorable artifacts in the history of higher education" and as "transitional object[s]" (p. 342) between the print and digital eras of academic publishing. Their study examined the contents of 110 course packs at Stanford University and Queen's University and found that 45 percent of all readings assigned were available in these institutions'

respective electronic collections. One barrier to the elimination of the course pack that Evans and Willinsky point to is the relative challenge of understanding what is in a particular collection and whether it can be shared with students electronically. They argue that the necessary socio-technical adjustment that must be undertaken to make the transition from using print to using electronic materials is often complex and bound to the two inertias of ingrained institutional practices and personal habits. Similarly, Vogl et al. (2012) identify the principal obstacle to moving away from the use of print materials to electronic collections as “the difficulty in identifying the content, and the uses of that content, that a school has already licensed for use by its community” (p. 6). Vogl et al.’s Stanford Intellectual Property Exchange (SIPX) offers a computational approach to overcoming this barrier - the tool identifies overlap between assigned course readings and materials available in the digital collections of libraries by “codifying” copyright law, license terms and library holdings. Lee’s study (2011) had previously pointed to the potential for this codification to produce cost savings through the elimination of “double payment” of copyright charges for material already paid for and licensed by the library. SIPX, recently acquired by Proquest (Proquest, 2015), offers a computational approach to the problem of the complexity of licensing and the resultant double payment for resources held in library electronic collections. (It is important to note that SIPX’s tool doesn’t fully account for uses of material that do not require permission and that do not require payment in the first place—there is not yet an algorithm that can conduct a fair use or fair dealing analysis.) Machine-readable license terms are becoming increasingly common (Jing et al., 2015; Ward et al., 2015) and are a growing way that instructors, researchers, publishers, and institutions can improve the usability of collections by embedding the answer to the question “can I use this this way?” into electronic systems.

Academic libraries have recently taken a more activist role in the provision of affordable course materials for students by making the reduction of student course materials costs the explicit goal of their programs and services. Christie et al. (2009) point to how traditional print reserves were already significant centers of cost savings for students who choose not to purchase required course materials. Blackburn and Tiemeyer (2013) point to why the decision to begin acquiring expensive textbooks on behalf of students is difficult—the large initial cost commitment. Bell (2015) details “model” OER textbook projects: the UCLA Affordable Course Materials Initiative promotes the adoption of freely-available resources through financial awards to faculty, while NCSU’s alternative textbook project does the same through the direct subsidization of the creation of course-specific content. The University of Maryland, University College (UMUC), has recently mandated the replacement of all of its undergraduate textbooks with “Embedded Digital Resources” developed or acquired by collaborative teams of faculty members, instructional designers and librarians (UMUC, 2015).

DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM

Outreach and Recruitment

The first step in implementing the pilot project was to design an outreach strategy that would secure the participation of instructors and their students. Beginning in the fall of 2014, the SCCO focused on outreach efforts with faculty from particular departments in the humanities and the social sciences, as instructors in these disciplines were among the heaviest users of course packs. The courses were largely third and fourth –year undergraduate classes, with only one graduate course selected for the pilot. The composition of the participating instructors was a fairly even mix of senior tenured faculty, teaching stream faculty, sessional lecturers, and graduate students. Most of these participating instructors were recruited through these efforts, which included sending personal emails to lists of instructors who would teach courses in the aforementioned disciplines during the upcoming Winter 2015 semester. The email pitch described the intent of the project—to reduce student costs—and the means—a collaborative consultation that would eliminate the need for the use of a course pack and that would locate the cost of the provision of materials to students within the library.

The ZTLCC pilot project was also a form of collections outreach. The University of Toronto’s collection is the largest in Canada and one of the most significant in the world, with approximately \$18 million (CAD\$) spent on electronic resources for the 2014-2015 fiscal year out of a total acquisitions and collections budget of approximately \$31 million (CAD\$). As mentioned above, part of the appeal of the project to some participating instructors was the pleasant realization that there were existing resources in the library collection that could be used to support their teaching and their students. This process of engagement served to educate faculty about the library collection, their rights to make use of these materials, and to encourage them to engage their students through its strengths. Another aspect of this outreach strategy was the promise to conscientiously take advantage of the rights and flexibilities that the Copyright Act provides to lower student costs.

Assessment and Evaluation

A secondary but nonetheless important part of the project’s outcome was to measure the value of a new e-reserve service at the University of Toronto, the Syllabus Service. Adopting a “full-service” model, the SCCO provided instructors at the University with copyright clearance of their syllabuses (including the purchasing of transactional licenses), links to electronic resources, scanning of compliant book excerpts and their hosting on library servers, and the placement of items on Short Term Loan. Like many services that

respond to an immediate need, the initial technological infrastructure supporting the Syllabus Service was built quickly—it performed its function but had few supplementary features, such as the ability to track and measure what was being made available via the service, either holistically or at an item level. Constrained by the tools at our disposal, with no means to collect metadata about what items were being shared through a new e-reserve service (which as per Cunningham above, was a costly investment), we used the ZTLCC as a means to create a snapshot of the cost-saving potential and value of the overall e-reserve service. The University of Toronto is a sprawling and decentralized environment—e-reserve services were offered by libraries across the institution’s multiple campuses at varying points along the full service vs. self-serve spectrum described by Goodsen and Frederiksen. Demonstrating the value of the service also made the case for the centralisation of these services into one access point where the copyright, licensing, access, and processing work could be more efficiently managed.

In order to calculate this snapshot of the cost-saving potential of the Syllabus Service, we surveyed course pack pricing at a number of copyshops identified by the University as being licensed by Access Copyright (Canada’s collective rights agency for written works) to produce course packs for the University of Toronto’s courses. As a result of this survey, we learned that course pack costs are broken down into three parts: binding cost, printing cost, and copyright cost. The binding costs varied depending on the type of binding chosen, with an average cost of \$5.31 per course pack. The printing costs at these authorized businesses also ranged in cost, the average being a cost of \$0.11 per page. The copyright charge for course packs, according to one copyshop representative is a standard \$0.05 per page for the Access Copyright license fee; for the purposes of our analysis, we used this \$0.05 per page charge. Armed with this data, we determined that the average per page cost for printing at the six surveyed copyshops was \$0.16. Together with our item-level collection of page data, we used the equation ($\$0.16 \times \text{total assigned pages}$) + \$5.31 to determine course pack prices for the materials assigned by the pilot’s participating courses.

With this formula, we could pass our item-level tracking of materials through our analytical framework, which was as follows: (a) create a sample of course packs; (b) identify the types of content that the instructor was assigning; (c) calculate how much it would cost to produce a course pack for the reading materials at a University of Toronto approved copyshop; (d) determine how much, if anything at all, the same course would cost relying on library licensed materials, the fair dealing exception, and transactional licensing; and (e) compare the hypothetical cost of creating a course pack and the cost of processing the course materials in house (which labour cost aside, was usually zero).

Figure 2. Single course pack cost for each of the pilot’s participating courses.

Figure 3. Combined course pack cost for each of the pilot’s participating courses.

This framework, together with the pilot project's item-level data collection, allowed us to measure how much assigned content, that is content that would have been paid for by students in course packs without the pilot, was already available in the digital or print collection, whether through an e-resource license, through fair dealing, or through the purchasing of an additional transactional license. In other words, this project has allowed us to track how much of the material in our sample that students would have purchased through course packs was already held in our collection, and in what format. We found that 55 percent of the pilot's course material was made available through licensed resources, mostly through links to electronic journal articles or multi-user e-books. In some cases, pdfs of these articles or chapters were provided if such provision of full-text copies was in accordance with the license associated with the electronic resource.² This finding—that a majority of assigned material was already available for use by students via electronic resources—suggests that double-payment remains an ongoing inefficiency in the way course materials are distributed and paid for. Expensive journal and e-book subscriptions are not being fully exploited, publisher revenues are inflated by double payments, and student and institutional expenditures are overlapping as a result. A further 38 percent of the materials provided through the project were scanned book excerpts made available in accordance with the University of Toronto's Fair Dealing Guidelines, which given the educational context and general disposition of the learning materials was interpreted as 10 percent or one chapter of a book, whichever was greater, as we have discussed above. The remainder of the materials were able to be distributed to students at no cost to the end-user, either through the purchase of licenses on their behalf or by linking to material legally available on the web (the project spent \$1193.57 on the purchase of 8 transactional licenses for book excerpts that exceeded fair dealing thresholds). By better connecting instructors and students to the collection and to the copyright and licensing expertise of library staff, the pilot project was able to demonstrate the existence of double-payment and take steps to reduce it (Figures 3, 4 & 5).

Challenges

While successful, the ZTLCC faced several challenges and will continue to face those challenges moving forward. The first challenge faced is maintaining the staffing to proceed with the work on an ongoing basis. While small relative to the size of the faculty and student body, the SCCO was staffed with the head of the unit, three librarians, one professional staff, and graduate student hours.

² The University of Toronto's instance of the OCUL Usage Rights (OUR) database presents license permissions for electronic resources directly in a resource's OPAC record. OUR lets a user know, for example, whether a resource can be shared in "Blackboard or course web pages." This technology made license review, a potentially painstaking task, relatively fast.

Figure 4. Items Assigned in Participating Winter 2015 Courses, Percentage by Type.

Figure 5. Percentage of All Assigned Book Excerpts by Availability in University of Toronto Libraries' E-Resource Collection.

Figure 6. Percentage of Materials Available in University of Toronto Libraries' E-Resource Collection.

Dedicating that level of resources to copyright and scholarly communications is only possible when those areas are prime institutional priorities. The second challenge faced was institutional appetite for copyright uncertainty. While Fair Dealing Guidelines like the ones at the University of Toronto have been supported many times by Canadian courts and administrative bodies, the fact that 38% of the content cleared by the ZTLCC was done so using the fair dealing exception might give risk-averse institutions pause in considering similar services, particularly in the United States, where, as we have discussed above, at least one jurisdiction has expressed unease at more definitive rules. Third, it is unclear whether there may be pedagogical drawbacks, as students do not retain access to their course materials with an electronic coursepack as they would with a printed one. (Pdfs can be saved, but access to links to electronic resources can expire in any number of ways, most commonly after a student graduates or leaves the institution). It is, however, possible that those potential pedagogical downsides might be negated by the increased affordances provided by digital texts.

NEXT STEPS

The ZTLCC project reveals two important lessons. First, it is clear that there is systemic double payment for course materials by students at the University of Toronto and almost certainly at other universities that have not undertaken systematic efforts to eliminate it. Second, there is a clear opportunity for libraries to provide a high impact and clearly quantifiable service to their students and their faculty.

The ZTLCC project is ongoing, and as of fall 2016 it has continued to reduce double payment by producing savings to students of \$406,038.65 so far. The majority of course materials made available through the project have continued to be licensed electronic resources, with a smaller but still significant number provided via the combination of U of Toronto's Fair Dealing Guidelines and the purchase of transactional licenses.

The project's approach to the recruitment of faculty and instructor participants has been tweaked to both demand less time from staff and to reflect the project's status as an established service of the library. The pilot relied on personal emails to faculty to market itself, but since this initial round of outreach the project has instead recruited participants via word of mouth as well as via a visible presence, especially of the costed assessment of results, on the Scholarly Communications & Copyright Office website, and in other library promotional materials. The project has also begun a collaboration with another initiative at the University, the Sustainability Office's well-established "Green Courses" project, to emphasize the reduction in printing demand that the use of digital materials in teaching affords. This collaboration has resulted in the addition of a new metric to our assessment package, that of "printed pages saved" (the total so far is approximately 1.7 million).

Since the launch of the ZTLCC pilot project in the fall of 2014, the University of Toronto Libraries has implemented a new e-reserve application, an open source product developed in-house by the University of British Columbia (UBC). The University of Toronto adopted this application, Library Online Course Reserves (LOCR), in advance of the Fall 2015 Term. This application is integrated with the University's supported learning management system, Blackboard, as well as with the library's catalogue, and allows for the greater and more sophisticated collection of metadata about the course materials that are distributed through the service that the system supports. These enhanced reporting features will allow us to replicate the item-level assessment we performed for the ZTLCC project but on a greater scale and will make future analysis both less arduous and more nimble and granular. The new application also stores scanned pdfs in a library and allows for the copyright-compliant reuse of these files when courses are taught again or when identical readings are assigned in other courses, cutting down on processing and access labor hours. It is hoped that future

iterations of the open source project will expand the kinds of data the application collects. Already, the SCCO is able to gain greater insight into the item types assigned to specific courses, as well as their respective copyright determinations. The copyright determination is particularly useful as it allows for an item to be labeled as licensed in the library's existing e-resource collection and made available for reuse. While item-level data collection has improved with the adoption of LOCR, expanding captured metadata to include publisher identity is planned for the future development of this open source application at the University, as gaining information about the nature and effects of scaled-up e-reserves services on the value of particular products becomes a possible assessment priority.

We have also now completed the Syllabus Service Terms of Service, which outlines how assigned course materials are processed and seeks to define the service level (via metrics such as overall processing time, email and communication response times, and policies regarding the provision of requested scans in cases where the instructor deems the electronic copy inferior to a pdf or unsuitable for their teaching needs). While the overarching goal of these terms is to create a more transparent service process, they will also help to create a more formalized system for determining the most cost-effective use of material and the efficient use of the library's collection.

One measure of success in this regard would be to, from a collection development perspective, increase the proportion of the project's assigned materials that are available in the University of Toronto's e-resource collection over time. As we have established, taking advantage of an e-resource collection allows faculty to assign course materials at no cost to students, and one effect of this is that faculty can assign a greater number or variety of readings without increasing student costs. An important point to note is that in our experience, faculty have been extremely willing to engage in the substitution of course materials if the high cost of those materials is brought to their attention. The continuing production of assessment data related to cost savings and the feeding back of this data into the marketing of services and, possibly, into the selection and assessment of collections, will be imperative to the project's continuing recruitment of new participants and relevance. Oakleaf (2010) has pointed out that it is very difficult to produce an overall monetary valuation of the many benefits of the suite of collections and services offered by academic libraries, but that the valuation of small, individual services is much more feasible. We expect that as the scale of e-reserves becomes larger, and as the composition of syllabuses change due to the increase in faculty flexibility, and the above noted irrelevance of material cost as a factor in the composition of reading lists, measuring syllabuses simply by their hypothetical cost as a course pack becomes less cogent as a reason why faculty might make use of the service. What will be needed then is a more holistic way to measure and describe all the forms of value provided by the collection.

Course	Students	Pages	Page Cost	Course Pack Cost	C o m b i n e d		Total Cost
					Page Cost	Binding Cost	
SWK4102	150	1483	\$237.28	\$242.59	\$35,592.00	\$796.50	\$36,388.50
SLA334	20	629	\$100.64	\$105.95	\$2,012.80	\$106.20	\$2,119.00
SOCC40	16	453	\$72.48	\$77.79	\$1,159.68	\$84.96	\$1,244.64
SOC218	130	814	\$130.24	\$135.55	\$16,931.20	\$690.30	\$17,621.50
SOC366	100	255	\$40.80	\$46.11	\$4,080.00	\$531.00	\$4,611.00
SOC371	100	505	\$80.80	\$86.11	\$8,080.00	\$531.00	\$8,611.00
SDS455	25	681	\$108.96	\$114.27	\$2,724.00	\$132.75	\$2,856.75
SOC413	25	694	\$111.04	\$116.35	\$2,776.00	\$132.75	\$2,908.75
POL301	70	578	\$92.48	\$97.79	\$6,473.60	\$371.70	\$6,845.30
SOC362	76	696	\$111.36	\$116.67	\$8,463.36	\$403.56	\$8,866.92
EMT2102	35	353	\$56.48	\$61.79	\$1,976.80	\$185.85	\$2,162.65
SOC279	130	589	\$94.24	\$99.55	\$12,251.20	\$690.30	\$12,941.50

Figure 7. Page and Binding Cost for Each Course: Note: Figures were calculated using data collected on course pack cost from 7 local copyshops (see Assessment and Evaluation).

Course	Students	Pages	Page Cost from Print	Page Cost of E-Resources	Total Print Cost	Total E-Resource Cost
SWK4102	150	1483	\$94.88	\$143.68	\$14,232.00	\$21,552.00
SLA334	20	629	\$76.80	\$23.84	\$1,536.00	\$476.80
SOCC40	16	453	\$49.60	\$22.88	\$793.60	\$366.08
SOC218	130	814	\$68.96	\$61.28	\$8,964.80	\$7,966.40
SOC366	100	255	\$0.00	\$40.96	\$0.00	\$4,096.00
SOC371	100	505	\$59.20	\$21.60	\$5,920.00	\$2,160.00
SDS455	25	681	\$54.56	\$54.56	\$1,364.00	\$1,364.00
SOC413	25	694	\$36.16	\$74.88	\$904.00	\$1,872.00
POL301	70	578	\$64.48	\$28.00	\$4,513.60	\$1,960.00
SOC362	76	696	\$10.56	\$100.80	\$802.56	\$7,660.80
EMT2102	35	353	\$39.52	\$16.96	\$1,383.20	\$593.60
SOC279	130	589	\$52.96	\$41.28	\$6,884.80	\$5,366.40

Figure 8. Print Cost and E-Resource Cost of Each Participating Course

REFERENCES

- Access Copyright v. CMEC, Copyright Board Canada (2016) Retrieved from <http://cb-cda.gc.ca/decisions/2016/DEC-K-122010-2015-19-02-06.pdf>
- Annand, D. (2008). Learning efficacy and cost-effectiveness of print versus e-book instructional material in an introductory financial accounting course. *Journal of Interactive Online Learning*, 7(2), 152-164.
- Bell, S. (2015). Start a Textbook Revolution, Continued: Librarians Lead the Way with Open Educational Resources. *Library Issues*, 35(5). <http://www.libraryissues.com/pub/PDF3505May2015.pdf>
- Berg, S. A., Hoffmann, K., & Dawson, D. (2010). Not on the same page: Undergraduates' information retrieval in electronic and print books. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 36(6), 518-525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2010.08.008>
- Black, E. L., & Blankenship, B. (2010). Linking students to library resources through the learning management system. *The Journal of Library Administration*, 50(5-6), 458-467. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2010.488587>
- Blackburn, G., & Tiemeyer, R. (2013). Textbooks and interlibrary loan. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 23(1), 5-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1072303X.2013.769040>
- Bridges, A. (2007). E-Reserves threatened at Cornell. *College and Research Libraries News*, 68(5), 317.
- CCH Canadian Ltd v Law Society of Upper Canada, 2004 SCC 13, McLachlin CJC.
- Chandler, J. (2016, February 2). The price of course readers are rising as a result of Ryerson letting its Access Copyright License expire. *The Eye Opener*. Retrieved from <http://theeyeopener.com/2016/02/damn-that-course-pack-is-expensive/>
- Christie, A., Pollitz, J. H., & Middleton, C. (2009). Student strategies for coping with textbook costs and the role of library course reserves. *portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 9(4), 491-510. doi:10.1353/pla.0.0077
- Cohen, N. (2008, September 14). Don't Buy That Textbook, Download It Free. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com/2008/09/15/technology/15link.html>
- Cunningham, K. (2010). The hidden costs of keeping current: Technology and libraries. *Journal of Library Administration*, 50(3), 217-235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930821003634955>
- Evans, B. J., & Willinsky, J. (2013). Setting aside the course reader: The legal, economic, and pedagogical reasons. *Innovative Higher Education*, 38(5), 341-354. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-012-9244-x>
- Farrington, R. (2015, July 30). The Simple Strategy to Stop Rising Tuition Costs. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <http://www.forbes.com/sites/robertfarrington/2015/07/30/the-simple-strategy-to-stop-rising-tuition-costs/#5302daff6eea>

- Financial Consumer Agency of Canada. (2014). Budget for student life-How much will your post-secondary education cost? Retrieved from <http://www.fcac-acfc.gc.ca/Eng/forConsumers/lifeEvents/payingPostSecEd/Pages/Budgetfo-Unbudget.aspx#books>
- Franklin, B., & Plum, T. (2008). Assessing the value and impact of digital content. *Journal of Library Administration*, 48(1), 41-57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930820802029334>
- Gardner, S., & Eng, S. (2005). What Students Want: Generation Y and the Changing Function of the Academic Library. *portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 5(3), 405-420. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2005.0034>
- Geist, M. (2014). Too Little, Too Late?: Access Copyright Finally Acknowledges the Reduced Value of Its License. Retrieved from <http://www.michaelgeist.ca/2014/12/little-late-access-copyright-finally-acknowledges-reduced-value-licence/>
- Giesecke, J. (2010). Finding the right metaphor: Restructuring, realigning, and repackaging today's research libraries. *Journal of Library Administration*, 51(1), 54-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2011.531641>
- Goodson, K. A., & Frederiksen, L. (2011). E-reserves in transition: Exploring new possibilities in E-reserves service delivery. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 21(1-2), 33-56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1072303X.2011.557976>
- Habib, M. (2013, September 11). University tuition rising to record levels in Canada. *CBC News*. Retrieved from <http://www.cbc.ca/news/canada/university-tuition-rising-to-record-levels-in-canada-1.1699103>
- Hudson, E. (September 2014) *Copyright Exceptions as Users' Rights? An Empirical Critique*. Paper presented to the IP Osgoode Speaker Series, Toronto, ON. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.osgoode.yorku.ca/ip-osgoode-videos/5/>
- Jing, J., Lin, Q., Sharifi, A., & Swartz, M. (2015). Making User Rights Clear: Adding e-resource License Information in Library Systems. *Code4Lib Journal*, (29).
- Katz, A. (2015) From Copyright Children to Copyright Adults. Retrieved from <http://arielkatz.org/archives/3578>
- Lee, F. (2011). An empirical analysis of costs, labor and copyright issues in course reader preparation: A case study of SIPX Spring 2011 Print on Demand deployment. *Unpublished Technical Report, Media X at Stanford University*, 6.
- Macdonald, D., & Shaker, E. (2014). *Tier for Two: Managing the Optics of Provincial Tuition Fee Policies*. Ottawa: Canadian Centre for Policy Alternatives.
- Mcgeveran, W., & Fisher, W. W. (2006). The Digital Learning Challenge: Obstacles to Educational Uses of Copyrighted Material in the Digital Age. *Berkman Center Research Publication*, (2006-09). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.923465>
- Nariani, R., & Fernandez, L. (2012). Open access publishing: What authors want. *College & Research Libraries*, 73(2), 182-195. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl-203>

Oakleaf, M. J., Association of College and Research Libraries., & American Library Association. (2010). *The value of academic libraries: A comprehensive research review and report*. Chicago, IL: Association of College and Research Libraries, American Library Association.

Proquest. (2015). ProQuest Acquires SIPX [Press release]. Retrieved from <http://www.proquest.com/about/news/2015/ProQuest-Acquires-SIPX.html>

Robin, I. (2014, September 21). After Access Copyright: Students report significant increase in course pack costs under new copyright arrangement. Retrieved from <http://thevarsity.ca/2014/09/21/after-access-copyright/>

University of California Los Angeles (UCLA) Library. (2016). Affordable Course Materials Initiative. Retrieved from <http://www.library.ucla.edu/support/support-instructors/affordable-course-materials-initiative>

University of Maryland, University College. (2015). Embedded Digital Resources Are In, Traditional Texts Out at UMUC: The Move Means Greater Access and Lower Costs for Students. Retrieved from <http://www.umuc.edu/globalmedia/embedded-digital-resources.cfm#sthash.DOlpCKMy.nIX824n2.dpbs>

The University of Toronto. (2012) (PDAD&C#26, 2012-13). Copyright Fair Dealing Guidelines. Retrieved from <http://www.provost.utoronto.ca/Assets/Provost+Digital+Assets/26.pdf>

United States Government Accountability Office. (2013). College Textbooks: Students Have Greater Access to Textbook Information. Retrieved from <http://www.gao.gov/products/GAO-13-368>

U.S. PIRG Education Fund & The Student PIRGs. (2014). Fixing the Broken Textbook Market. Retrieved from <http://www.uspirg.org/reports/usp/fixing-broken-textbook-market>

Usher, A. (2015). Data on Textbook Costs. *Higher Education Strategy Associates*. Retrieved from <http://higheredstrategy.com/data-on-textbook-costs/>

Vogl, R., Lee, F., Russell, M. G., & Genesereth, M. (2012). Addressing the Copyright Law Barrier in Higher Education – Access-to-Clean-Content Technology in the 21st Century. Retrieved from http://web.stanford.edu/group/codex/cgi-bin/codex/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/sipx_wp_copyright_law_barrier_2012-06.pdf

Ward, K.J., Bilder, G., & Callahan, C., (2015). Crossref REST API. *GitHub repository*. Retrieved from https://github.com/CrossRef/rest-api-doc/blob/master/rest_api.md

Warlick, S. E., & Vaughan, K. T. L. (2007). Factors influencing publication choice: why faculty choose open access. *Biomedical digital libraries*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-5581-4-1>